

Optimization of Router Cost and Consumption in a Point-to-Multipoint Metro-Core Architecture

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Abstract: We study the router cost and power consumption in a light-tree based architecture with coherent point-to-multipoint (P2MP) transceivers. Significant savings are expected compared to existing P2MP approaches due to router consolidation deeper in the metro-core. © 2025 The Author(s)

1. Introduction

With the advent of coherent P2MP transceivers that utilize digital subcarriers (DSCs), network operators have now access to unique features that introduce enhanced flexibility in resource allocation [1]. P2MP hub transceivers can broadcast to multiple spokes, thus providing a significant cost improvement over point-to-point (P2P) connections. Traditionally, the P2MP approach has been applied in the access-metro part of the network to facilitate the communication of access aggregators (spokes) and metro-core nodes (hubs) over a horseshoe or ring. Recently, we extended this “hub-and-spoke” (H&S) paradigm for operation over the metro-core mesh via the utilization of light-trees (LTs), which allow for the migration of hubs deeper into the metro-core and closer to the backbone [2]. Compared to the H&S architecture, the LT approach was shown to be even more cost-effective, further reducing the required transceivers’ number. An unexplored aspect of the LT architecture, however, relates to traffic aggregation in the IP layer. Previous works on P2MP architectures suggest that it is possible to bypass router hierarchies [3], which introduces significant cost savings for operators, and the LT architecture exhibits a similar potential.

Fig. 1 illustrates the idea behind the router bypass in P2MP architectures. The reference is the baseline H&S architecture (a) that deploys hubs in metro-core nodes (red squares) at the borders between the horseshoes and the metro-core mesh: routers are required at each horseshoe endpoint to aggregate the traffic and forward it with P2P connections to the backbone (green hexagon) and/or a datacenter. Using LTs that built upon the entire physical topology (horseshoes plus metro-core), the P2MP hubs are reduced in number (b) as several of them can be consolidated at the same metro-core node. A further optimization step (c) can be achieved by reducing the metro-core nodes in which P2MP hubs and aggregation routers are placed. Consequently, the optimized LT architecture will require a smaller number of higher capacity routers, which are relatively cheaper and consume less power. Both aspects are studied in this work

Fig. 1. (a) Baseline H&S, (b) LT and (c) LT-optimized P2MP architectures. UL/DL: up/downlink; SC: subcarrier.

and it is shown that the LT architecture can impart up to 66% cost and 60% power consumption saving compared to the baseline H&S architecture for a realistic network topology and traffic scenario.

2. Network Topology and Equipment

The simulated topology is shown in Fig. 2 and was inspired by the TIM metro-aggregation and metro-core networks. The aggregation network consisted of 342 aggregators that were connected to the metro-core mesh through 87 horse-shoes with a total average length of 105.5 km (17.6 to 434 km) and an average link length of 21.4 km (1.8 to 75.3 km). The metro-core network mesh was formed from 139 fiber links with lengths varying from 1.4 to 110.2 km that interconnected 95 metro-core nodes (potential hubs). Among these, 5 national nodes were connected to the backbone network, 66 nodes collected traffic from the horseshoes, 23 nodes acted as routing intermediaries without a horseshoe and one node hosted the datacenter. The aggregators collectively generated 35.8 Tb/s of traffic on average, while each aggregator generated from 11 to 364 Gb/s and was served using a P2MP spoke transceiver with the corresponding capacity. The communication of the spoke with its hub took place using 4 GBaud DSCs. For fixed transceivers, a 16-QAM modulation format was used, while we also studied the use of flexible transceivers that could utilize lower-order modulations such as 8-QAM, QPSK, or BPSK to adjust for varying OSNRs. The transceiver sizes were available in configurations of {4, 8, 16, 32} DSCs, each carrying a maximum capacity of 25 Gb/s at 16-QAM employing dual-polarization. The traffic from the hubs was forwarded to the backbone and the datacenter, with 50% of the traffic being directed to each destination. A router was required at each hub location, and cost and energy savings were obtained if we avoided placing routers at intermediate nodes apart from the desired backbone nodes or datacenter. Four types of routers were considered, denoted as {Small, Medium, Large, Extra-Large}, with a maximum respective capacity of {400, 1600, 3200, 6400} Gb/s and a cost of {0.6, 1.6, 2.8, 2.8} arbitrary units (a.u). Based on internal data and measurements, the power consumption of each router increased linearly between {(125, 250), (175, 350), (230, 460), (310, 620)} W, where the first value corresponds to the idle state and the second to operation at full capacity.

3. Router Placement Algorithm, Results and Discussion

The router placement algorithm involved three steps, with the first being the LT formation. This task is challenging due to the problem size and involves (a) the selection of the modulation format of each spoke transceiver based on the OSNR, (b) the assignment of spokes to hubs based on their requested capacity, and (c) the placement of hubs on metro-core nodes. We previously proposed a heuristic algorithm to solve the problem almost optimally and generate the LTs and the possible hub placement nodes [2]. Briefly, the algorithm sorts the spoke requests in a descending order and utilizes the highest eligible modulation order to assign them to hubs. The hub placement is then determined by the metro-core and backbone nodes that are reachable from all spokes in the LT. To calculate the reach of each spoke, we considered an OSNR level at the horseshoe endpoints equal to $OSNR_h(dB) = 15.1 + budget$, where 15.1 dB is the 16-QAM sensitivity [4] and the extra budget is determined from the horseshoe topology [5]. The metro-core OSNR was estimated via simulations with the GN model, assuming a worst-case scenario where 32 LTs (4.1 THz bandwidth) co-exist over the same links. An approximation for the metro-core OSNR was given by $OSNR_m(dB) = 26.0 - 10 \log_{10}(2N_s)$, where N_s is the number of 80 km equivalent links that are traversed and a factor of two is used to quantify the ROADMs impairments, assuming that their impact is comparable to that of the optical links. In this first step, the hubs can be potentially placed at multiple metro-core nodes, depending on the available OSNR, and in the second step of the algorithm we limit these options and determine the minimum number of metro-core and backbone

Fig. 2. Router placement over the topology. (a) Fixed transceivers with 0 dB budget, (b) flexible transceivers with 0 dB budget, (c) both transceiver types with 4 dB budget. The line thickness is proportional to the density of LTs.

Fig. 3. Router (a) size distribution, (b) cost and (c) power consumption.

nodes that must host at least one hub. This corresponds to solving the classic hitting-set problem and is performed optimally using integer linear programming. In third and final step, the hubs are assigned to the hitting-set nodes, starting with the node with the highest possible hub count. The process is repeated until all nodes have been examined, selecting at each iteration the node with the highest remaining hub count. Simultaneously, the router capacity of the node is determined from the sum traffic of the hosted hubs. It is then ensured that the minimum number of metro-core and backbone nodes host routers and that the routers serve the maximum possible capacity.

A visualization of the algorithm is performed in Fig. 2. Fig. 2(a), where the transceivers are fixed and no budget is available, shows that no LTs are formed and that the hubs are placed at the horseshoe endpoints, similar to the reference H&S. In total, 37 nodes are equipped with routers (32 regional, 4 national, 1 datacenter) and the number of routers equals 41, since the datacenter and one of the national nodes require 3 routers each. If flexible transceivers are utilized then LTs are formed, and the hubs are placed deeper in the metro-core; Fig. 2(b) shows that routers are moved from the regional nodes and are consolidated with the routers at the 4 national nodes. The number of routers reduces to 12, since the national node that previously hosted 3 routers now hosts 6. If the OSNR budget is increased to 4 dB, then all transceivers utilize 16-QAM, and this results in the most efficient solution of Fig. 2(c). The routers from all national nodes are moved and consolidated at a single location with 6 routers, reducing the total router count to 9. The consolidation process also results in the utilization of extra-large routers with reduced cost and consumption, and the resulting router distribution for the three cases of Fig. 2 is depicted in Fig. 3(a), along with an intermediate case where the budget is 2 dB (5 nodes - 10 routers). The corresponding cost evolution with the OSNR budget is presented in Fig. 3(b), and it can be verified that a budget of 1 or 2 dB is adequate for a drastic cost cut in the LT architecture with fixed transceivers. The cost stabilizes at higher budgets and the LT architecture reduces the router cost by 66% compared to the baseline H&S. Flex transceivers provide additional cost savings at lower budgets, and the cost reduction ranges between 60% and 66%. A similar trend is observed for router consumption, which also reduces significantly with the available budget when transceivers are fixed and is almost flat when transceivers are flexible. Fixed transceivers reduce power consumption by almost 60%, while flexible transceivers attain savings between 54% and 60%.

3. Conclusion

We have presented results on the optimization of router count, cost and power consumption in a P2MP metro-core architecture. The optimization is achieved using LTs that enable the migration of routers and their consolidation in the backbone nodes of the metro-core network. This process reduces the router count and increases the capacity per router, leading to significant cost and consumption savings. In a realistic network scenario, the router cost can be reduced by 66%, while the energy savings can reach up to 60%.

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